

MOTIVATING PERSONNEL IN CONDITIONS OF FINANCIAL INSTABILITY OF THE COMPANY.

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15396918>

In conditions of financial instability, companies are faced with the need to maintain staff efficiency with limited resources. Revenue reduction, salary freezes, reduction of bonuses and social benefits have a negative impact on employee morale, which entails a drop in productivity and an increase in staff turnover. However, it is precisely during a crisis that the role of non-material motivation increases, and management is obliged to seek flexible and non-standard approaches to stimulating the team.

The purpose of this thesis is to analyze effective methods of motivating personnel in conditions of limited budget and unstable financial situation, as well as to develop practical recommendations for increasing employee engagement.

Key aspects of the study include:

1. Identification of priority non-material incentives for employees in crisis conditions.

Understanding which forms of non-material incentives are most significant for staff (flexible hours, recognition, career growth) allows for the effective redistribution of the company's internal resources.

2. Analysis of the relationship between the level of employee engagement and loyalty and corporate culture.

Research shows that in uncertain times, employees are more likely to stay with companies that have a strong and supportive culture based on trust, respect, and openness. Creating transparent communication channels, employee participation in discussions of current issues, and regular feedback from management help to increase trust and emotional attachment to the company. An important element is the example set by management – the behavior of top managers has a direct impact on the emotional climate in the team.

2. Study of successful cases of companies that have maintained team stability without increasing the payroll fund.

Specific strategies for retaining staff in times of crisis are analyzed using examples from local and international companies. These include: implementing recognition programs. (Employee of the Month, letters of thanks from

management), organizing training initiatives within the company, temporary rotation of employees to develop new competencies, and providing the opportunity to work on projects with a high degree of autonomy. These measures help maintain motivation, develop skills, and create a sense of value for each employee, even if salary increases are not possible.

Recommendations for increasing motivation include:

1. Development of a transparent system of internal communications.
2. Involvement of employees in the decision-making and strategic planning process.
3. Recognition and encouragement of merits (non-material bonuses, certificates, public gratitude).
4. Flexible work schedule and opportunities for growth (training, career prospects).
5. Strengthening corporate culture based on trust and mutual assistance

Thus, an effective motivation system in a crisis should be based not so much on financial resources as on values, recognition and involvement of personnel, which in the long term helps to strengthen the team and increase business sustainability.

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